

PREPARATION OF HETEROGENOUS CATALYST OF ACEH COW BONE MATERIAL AND ITS CATALYTIC PERFORMANCE FOR BIODIESEL SYNTHESIS

Rara Mitaphonna, Muliadi Ramli, Ilham Maulana, Desi Novita, Intan Zahara and Rizki Wardani

Chemistry Department, Syiah Kuala University, Darussalam- Banda Aceh

Email: raramitaphonna11@gmail.com

Abstract.

This study was focused on the utilization of cow bones found in Aceh as a raw material for heterogenous catalyst preparation and study of its catalytic performance on transesterification reaction using castor oil as methyl ester (biodiesel). The catalyst was prepared by thermal decomposition method calcined at 900°C in atmospheric air for 4 hours of its calcined time. The characterization of prepared catalysts were carried out using X-ray diffraction (XRD), where as the profile of the XRD diffractogram resulted from the prepared catalysts showing specific diffraction as the $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{OH})$ and CaO diffractogram, as it has been reported on JCPDS system. The characterization catalyst using SEM-EDS show that the catalyst has a homogenous morphology. Based on GC-MS chromatogram of the transesterification product, it could be noted that the FAMES already produced in this experiment, The main compound produced from the transesterification process catalyzed by the prepared catalyst in this work was ricinoleate methyl esters with a percentage is 58.75%. The synthesized biodiesel has acid number, viscosity and density was 0.183 mg KOH / g, 5.4 mm²/s and 0.8456 g/ mol, respectively.

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1. Introduction

Along with the high interest of Acehnese beef, Aceh cow production increased significantly. According to data from the Indonesian Beef Cow Farmers Association or GAPUSPINDO (2016), beef consumption per kilogram per capita per year from 2016 to 2020 will experience an average increase of 5%. Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency (2016), Indonesia's beef production in 2016 reached 524,109 tons, of which the province of Aceh alone contributed a total production of 10,550 tons. The amount of Aceh beef demand increased when the commemoration of Eid al-Adha was to be used as a sacrificial animal. Especially in the province of Aceh, the need for Aceh beef increased significantly due to the commemoration of Maulid Rasulullah SAW, the day was held in several editions such as before Ramadhan, Eid al-Fitr or Eid al-Adha.

In the process of processing beef, parts of the cow's body that are not useful, such as bone, are disposed of wastefully and become waste for the environment. Increased consumption of beef in the province of Aceh, will correlate with the availability of beef bone waste in Aceh which also increases. Wasted cow bones will become environmental pollution because they are often discarded without supervision. To deal with this, special measures are needed so that livestock waste such as cow bones does not become waste. Some solutions that have been done by the community are using cow bones as raw material for making organic fertilizers, handicrafts and bone meal [1]. Utilization of cow bone waste as a supporting product of

chemical processes has been carried out by utilizing bovine bone waste as a heterogeneous catalyst in the esterification process to reduce the acid waste of edible oil [2]. Processing animal bones as a calcium-based catalyst in environmentally friendly energy synthesis [3]. Utilization of animal bones was also carried out by processing animal bones as heterogeneous catalysts for biodiesel synthesis. This study uses potassium hydroxide (KOH) as a catalyst support to increase its catalytic activity [4].

The catalyst used in the biodiesel synthesis reaction is generally alkaline because it has higher catalytic activity and is not corrosive [5]. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), potassium hydroxide (KOH) and calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) are homogeneous base catalysts that are often used in biodiesel synthesis reactions. However, the use of homogeneous base catalysts causes problems, which is difficult to separate from the product so that further purification is required at a high cost. The use of heterogeneous catalysts is an alternative to replace homogeneous catalysts because they are easily separated from the product, do not require high costs for the purification process and minimize the waste produced [6]. Heterogeneous catalysts derived from alkali metal oxides such as CaO, MgO, and SrO have been widely developed by previous researchers because they have high activity and alkalinity that are capable of producing high percentage of biodiesel at low temperatures [7]. However, the use of alkali metal oxide as a heterogeneous catalyst has a relatively expensive price so it is not economical to use. Therefore, environmentally friendly raw materials are needed for the synthesis of heterogeneous catalysts. Previous research has used several types of solid waste such as mollusks, eggshells, seashells and cow bones as raw material for the synthesis of heterogeneous catalysts [8]. Among the solid waste used, Aceh beef bone is one source for the synthesis of heterogeneous catalysts because it is easy to find and abundant in Aceh province.

Heterogeneous catalyst prepared from the bones of Aceh cow will be tested for activity on the transesterification reaction of castor oil. Production of biodiesel through the transesterification reaction currently using raw materials from plant oils can be consumed [9]. The use of oil that can be consumed will create food problems in developing countries. Therefore, a potential replacement for raw materials for biodiesel production is needed. Plant oil cannot be consumed such as castor oil is a good alternative for biodiesel production because it cannot be consumed, is toxic and has low economic value [10]. In addition, the essential fatty acid content in castor oil is so low that it cannot be used as edible oil and foodstuffs. Aceh cow bone is used as raw material for the synthesis of heterogeneous catalysts to utilize inorganic compounds in the bones of cow. In order for all the inorganic components of bovine bone to be utilized optimally as a biodiesel catalyst heterogeneous, it is necessary to do detailed research on this. This research is also a form of concern for the environment while reducing the amount of cow bone waste in the province of Aceh.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Materials were used Aceh cow bone, castor oil, methanol 99%, KOH 0.1 N, anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , H_2SO_4 , phenolptalein indicator (pp), aquabides and distilled water.

2.2. Work procedures

2.2.1 Heterogeneous catalyst preparation

Fresh Aceh cow bones from the Lhokseumawe market are cleaned and washed to remove dust, meat, fat and cartilage attached to the bones. Furthermore, cow bones are dried in an oven at 110°C for 5 hours and cooled at room temperature [4]. Then, the bone of the cow is

destroyed by using an iron mortar to form a powder. Sifted beef bone powder using a 100 mesh sieve. Furthermore, cow bone powder was calcined at 900 ° C for 4 hours and tested for activity as a catalyst in the transesterification reaction of castor oil.

2.2.2. Characterization of catalysts

Determination of the composition of compounds in the material was analyzed using X-ray Diffraction (XRD). Meanwhile, the determination of surface morphology and percentage of elements in the material were analyzed using Scanning Electron Microscope-Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS).

2.2.3. Oil quality test

2.2.3.1. Determination of acid numbers

2.2.3.2. Determination of water content

2.2.3.3. Determination of density

2.2.3.4. Determination of viscosity

2.2.4. Synthesis of biodiesel

2.2.4.1. Esterification reaction of castor oil

Castor oil is filtered and heated at 105 ° C for 1 hour to remove impurities and water content. Furthermore, castor oil is put into a three-neck flask and methanol is added in a ratio of 12: 1 mole. Then added 0.8 mL H₂SO₄. Furthermore, the mixture was stirred using a magnetic stirrer and heated at 65 ° C for 90 minutes [4]. The results of the esterification reaction were allowed to stand for 24 hours and two layers were expected to form. The upper layer is triglycerides, while the lower layer is water. The top layer is separated using a separating funnel and taken for the next transesterification reaction.

2.2.4.2. Transesterification reaction of castor oil

Triglycerides produced from the esterification reaction are heated for 30 minutes at 50 ° C. Furthermore, the catalyst was added as much as 6% (w / w) of oil which had been prepared into methanol and stirred using a magnetic stirrer for 15 minutes. Then, the mixture is inserted into the triglycerides resulting from the esterification reaction. All ingredients are put into a three-neck flask on a set of reflux devices equipped with a thermometer and magnetic stirrer. Transesterification reaction was carried out at 60 ° C and stirred using a magnetic stirrer for 3 hours. Transesterification reaction results are allowed to stand for 24 hours and 2 layers are expected to form. The top layer is methyl ester and the lower layer is glycerol.

2.2.4.3. Washing and purifying biodiesel

Glycerol is separated from crude glycerol by slowly opening the valve on the separating funnel. Crude biodiesel is washed using warm water at 50 ° C in a ratio of 1: 1. Then, the mixture is shaken for 5 minutes to dissolve the remaining methanol and glycerol. Next, leave the mixture for 24 hours and 2 layers will form. The bright top layer is biodiesel while the milk-colored lower layer is an emulsion mixed with washing water. Biodiesel was separated from the emulsion and analyzed using GC-MS to see the content and percentage of methyl esters in biodiesel [11].

2.2.5 Biodiesel quality test

The biodiesel quality test includes determination of acid numbers, viscosity, moisture content and density. Determination of the quality of biodiesel is done the same as determining oil quality. The biodiesel produced in this study was analyzed using GC-MS to see the content and percentage of methyl esters in biodiesel.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Heterogeneous catalyst preparation

Heterogeneous catalyst preparation from Aceh cattle bone waste was carried out by following previous studies by Nisar et al. (2017). Calcination at 900 ° C is the best calcination condition according to research conducted by Nisar et al. (2017), where the percentage of biodiesel produced reached 96.1%. Calcination aims to remove carbon dioxide (CO₂) compounds in the bones of the cow and turn the compounds into oxide form so that the surface area of the material increases. The results obtained from the calcination process are fine white materials. The material is ready to be tested for activity as a catalyst in the transesterification reaction of castor oil to produce biodiesel. Before calcined cow bone particles have a rather coarse texture, but after calcined cow bone particles have a smooth texture with a lighter mass.

3.2. Characterization materials

3.2.1. X-ray Diffraction (XRD)

Based on adjustments to the JCPDS database, fresh Aceh cow bone powder produces calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) with two phases, namely calcite and aragonite (Figure 3.1.). The formation of calcite can be seen in diffraction peaks which are marked by row parallelogram with an angle of 2θ: 25.9200 °, 32.130 ° and 35.4700 °. Aragonite can be seen at angles 2θ: 23.1050 °, 28.8900 ° and 39.7800 °. In addition, powder fresh Aceh cow bone also contains hydroxyapatite ((Ca)₅(PO₄)₃(OH)) at an angle of 2θ: 34.2200 °. Based on the diffractogram obtained, Aceh beef bone which was calcined at 900°C for 4 hours produced a new peak shows that new compounds have been formed such as CaO and Ca(OH)₂, as well as increasing the intensity of hydroxyapatite. Diffraction peaks at an angle of 2θ: 31.8499 °, 32.9875 ° and 39.8804 ° indicate the formation of hydroxyapatite as the main ingredient in the material. The peaks at 2θ: 32.2768 ° and 35.5528 ° shows CaO formation and 2θ: 18.8725 °, 28.5600 ° and 34.1423 ° angles indicate the formation of Ca(OH)₂.

Figure 1. XRD diffractogram of bovine bone material (a) before calcined (b) after calcined

3.2.2. Scanning Electron Microscope - Energy Dispersion Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS)

The results of SEM analysis showed that uncalcinated cow bone material had an inhomogeneous morphology that formed coarse aggregates and still contained organic compounds (Figure 3.2.). Previous research explains that animal bones that are not calcined show morphology that forms aggregates with small surface area and larger particle size [4]. While the calcined material shows a change in morphology, the organic compounds have been decomposed and the inorganic compounds have changed to the oxide form which is

characterized by the formation of a homogeneous and smooth morphology. This shows that the effect of calcination causes the conversion of compounds to their oxide form so that the material is more crystalline. This facilitates the process of adsorption between reactants and catalysts so that the chemical reaction takes place quickly.

Figure 2. SEM mikrograf of bovine material (a) before calcined (b) after calcined

EDS testing aims to determine the percentage of elements and chemical compounds contained in the material. Table 3.1. showed that non-calcined material containing inorganic content consisted mainly of calcium (Ca) of 18.66%, phosphorus (P) of 11.61% and oxygen (O) 41.44% and several small

Table 1. EDS analysis of calcined cow bones and uncalcined cow bones

Elemen	Weight uncalcined cow bones (%)	Atomic uncalcined cow bones (%)	Weight calcined cow bones (%)	Atomic calcined cow bones (%)
C K	27.42	39.70	11.07	18.11
O K	41.44	45.05	48.65	59.77
Na K	0.56	0.42	-	-
Mg K	0.31	0.22	0.69	0.56
P K	11.61	6.52	14.68	9.31
Ca K	18.66	8.10	24.37	11.95
Cl K	-	-	0.55	0.30
Total	100		100	

components such as sodium (Na) and magnesium (Mg). However, on the calcined material the content of Ca, O and P increased to 24.37%, 14.68% and 48.65% which confirmed that the material was dominated by $(Ca)_5(PO_4)_3(OH)$ with an increase in composition in the element Ca, P and O and supported by XRD data that compounds formed in 900 ° C calcination material are $(Ca)_5(PO_4)_3(OH)$ as the main content based on XRD peak intensity which reaches 1000 rails. Increased elements of Ca, P and O in calcined materials, the calcination process was able to decompose organic compounds in the material, which was also evidenced by a decrease in the percentage of element C in calcined material from 27.42% to 11.07% so that a decrease in

the percentage of organic elements inside material, there is an increase in inorganic elements in the material.

3.3. Biodiesel Synthesis

Biodiesel synthesis is carried out using uncalcined cow bone material and using calcined material. Before the transesterification reaction is carried out, castor oil must undergo an esterification reaction first. The result of the esterification reaction is the formation of two layers. The upper layer is the triglyceride layer, while the lower layer is the water layer. Triglycerides are separated from the water layer for further transesterification reactions. The results of the esterification reaction of castor oil resulted in a decrease in acid number from 1,757 mg KOH / g to 0.832 mg KOH / g. The results obtained from the transesterification reaction of castor oil are the formation of two layers. The two layers are allowed to stand for 24 hours so that the catalyst is deposited so as to facilitate the separation process. The top layer is crude methyl ester (biodiesel), while the lower layer is glycerol, residual methanol and catalyst. Then, the two layers are separated using a separating funnel. Crude biodiesel is taken and washed using warm water several times to remove the water content, glycerol and residual methanol. The purified biodiesel product was analyzed using GC-MS to see whether the biodiesel reaction product formed biodiesel and saw the methyl ester content in the sample.

Transesterification reaction of castor oil was also carried out using non-calcined material. The results obtained are the formation of 2 layers, but the upper layer is a clear methanol layer and the bottom layer is a layer of oil. After completing the transesterification reaction, there was no change in the color of methanol and oil so it can be concluded that biodiesel is not formed using bone material of Aceh cattle that are not calcined. In addition, the top layer (methanol) is also analyzed for density to determine whether methanol is formed correctly. Based on the research conducted, the upper layer has a density of 0.79 g / mL which indicates that this value is the value of methanol density in general so that the top layer is truly a methanol layer. This shows that the material without calcination has no activity on the transesterification reaction.

3.4. GC-MS analysis

Transesterification reaction of castor oil produced 4 methyl esters identified by GC-MS, namely methyl palmitate (17.56%), methyl oleate (8.37%), methyl stearate (6.22%) and methyl risinoleate (58.74%) as the largest content in the sample. The high risinoleic methyl esters in biodiesel synthesized are thought to be due to the castor oil used as raw material for castor oil (*Ricinus communis*). Content of fatty acids in castor oil (*Ricinus communis*) was dominated by ricinoleic acid by 89.5% [12]. Ricinoleic acid is an unsaturated fatty acid with 18 carbon atoms that have a hydroxyl group on the 12th carbon atom. So it can be concluded that the biodiesel synthesized comes from *Ricinus communis* so that the methyl ester in the biodiesel is dominated by methyl esters risinoleate.

Table 2. GC-MS chromatogram biodiesel for castor oil

Peaks numbers	Retention times (minutes)	Peaks area (%)	Composition
1.	20.087	7.53	Methyl palmitat
2.	20.371	10.03	Methyl palmitat

3.	24.399	8.37	Methyl oleat
4.	24.492	9.11	Methyl oleat
5.	25.207	6.22	Methyl stearat
6.	28.622	58.74	Methyl risinoleat

3.5. Biodiesel Quality Test

Biodiesel obtained was analyzed for water content, pH, acid number, density and viscosity and compared with biodiesel values according to Indonesian National Standard (SNI) 7182: 2015 [13]. Table 3.3. shows the value of acid number, pH, density and density of biodiesel synthesized from castor oil.

Table 3. Characteristics of biodiesel produced by synthesis

No.	Parameter	Biodiesel	SNI	Unit
1.	Color	Bening	-	-
2.	Acid value	0.130	0.8	mg KOH/g
3.	pH	6.2	-	-
4.	Viscosity	5.4	2.3-6.0	cSt
5.	Density	0.8596	0.85-0.90	g/cm ³

4. Conclusion

Based on the research that has been done, it can be concluded that the heterogeneous catalysts from Aceh cow bones have been successfully prepared. Heterogeneous catalysts ((Ca₅(PO₄)₃(OH) and CaO) have activity in the transesterification reaction of castor oil to produce biodiesel. Biodiesel synthesized from castor oil containing risinoleic methyl ester as the largest content with a percentage of 58.74% and has acid value, density, and viscosity that meet SNI that is 0.130 mg KOH / g, 0.8596 g / mL and 5.4 cSt. Ca₅(PO₄)₃(OH) and CaO obtained can be used in other vegetable oil transesterification reactions to produce biodiesel based on a decrease in acid value, density and viscosity of the biodiesel produced.

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